

DIRECTLY MASS-PRODUCTION GROWING METHOD OF CNT AEROGEL WITH SUPERB LIQUID-ABSORPTION CAPABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Nano porous materials, such as grapheme sponge, foam and SiO₂ aerogel, have recently attracted a great deal of attention because of their light-weight, extremely high specific surface, and potential for heat insulation, noise reduction, energy-absorbing and energy-storage. Because carbon nanotube (CNT) has high aspect ratio, amazing thermal and electrical conduction^[1], it also plays important roles in constituting porous materials. Moreover, lots of studies have been done on CNT foams with most of them made from intermittent methods, such as sol-gel and chemical vapor deposition. Here, a kind of CNT aerogel, which is growing by floating catalyst chemical vapor deposition method (FCCVD), is introduced. In order to get ideal CNT aerogel, we modified growing conditions to control the CNTs fabrication in the reaction zone. The result shows that in hydrogen and argon atmosphere, ethanol with 1% ferrocene and thiophene atomized and injected in to quartz tube with the reaction zone temperature around 1300°C will get excellent self-assembling interconnected 3D CNT network. After a certain period collection, network stacks at the tube end and form a cylindrical aerogel with 53 mm in height and 38 mm in diameter. This kind of aerogel gets 12.8 mg/cm³ in density and shows remarkable flexibility. What is more, the aerogel is super hydrophobic, which indicates that it will not absorb water and can collapse itself in moisture environment. It also has great capability of oil-absorption, which can absorb more than 90 times of its own weight of oil and organic solvent, such as acetone. It also has good sorption-squeezing and thermal stability properties, which means that the solvent absorbed can be squeezed out or burned. Thus, it could be a recyclable sorbent for oil and organic solvents. This CNT aerogel directly grows from gaseous phase rather than liquid phase (required in sol-gel method), which makes aerogel fabrication easier. Moreover, compared with other method, the FCCVD method can continuously produce, which means this is a low-cost and suitable for industrial production way to produce oils and organic solvents clean aerogel.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aerogel is a kind of material with developed pore structure. This three-dimensional porous structure has ultra-low density, small thermal conductivity, and high porosity, attracting more and more attentions^[2, 3]. In 1931, S.S.Kistler et al^[4] first prepared SiO₂ aerogel structure with sol-gel method and the supercritical drying technology in Stanford University, which created a precedent of aerogel. Subsequently, the successful application of SiO₂ aerogels in the field of Cerenkov detector and insulation materials greatly stimulate the researches of aerogel materials^[5]. Meanwhile, other metal oxides, such as Al₂O₃, TiO₂, and B₂O₃, MoO₂, MgO, ZrO₂, SnO₂, Nb₂O₅ and Cr₂O₃, were used to build 3D structure aerogels^[6].

Discovery of carbon aerogel is a milestone in the history of the development of aerogels^[2]. On one hand, carbon aerogels has the main advantages of conventional aerogels. On the other hand, because of the electrical properties of carbon materials, carbon aerogels have more extensive application than

the inorganic oxide gel. For example, the carbon aerogel electrodes can be used to build a super capacitor and lithium ion battery^[7]. Carbon aerogels usually use resorcinol and formaldehyde as the raw material in the process of preparation, and then form organic gel with the acidic or alkaline catalysts. Finally, carbon aerogels are obtained by subsequent supercritical drying and carbonization process^[8].

Carbon nanotube (CNT) is a new favor in material science during recent decades^[9], and attracts thousands of researchers to study the properties and application for years due to its unique structure and a series of excellent properties. In order to transfer the excellent properties of single nanotube into the properties of macroscopic application, CNT assembly structures become an advanced research hotspot. Among them, CNT aerogel, called as CNT sponge and CNT foam, is a significant research direction. CNT aerogel was first produced as intermediate phases during CNT sheets or fibers production, which are easily collapsed, and the first free-standing CNT aerogel was fabricated by Zou at 2010^[10]. He synthesized a kind of MWCNT with the density of 4 mg/cm³, which is much lighter than SiO₂ aerogels (20mg/cm³). And he found the CNT aerogel got excellent compression recoverable property which SiO₂ aerogel is hard to get. That out-standing properties are contributed to the different aggregation morphology. Due to the great aspect ratio of CNTs, the porous structure of CNT aerogel comes from CNT interconnection, other than the stacking and crosslink of nanoparticles. The CNT interconnection forms continuous fibrous supporting network, which are more flexible to bear more compressive force.

With the increasingly drawn attention of CNT aerogel, more fantastic properties are found, in which Oil absorption capability is a central issue^[11, 12]. Environment crisis is a worldwide problem from 1980's, and oil spilled in the sea is one serious issue causing environment pollution. On 20th April 2010, Transocean's Deepwater Horizon oil rig exploded and caused more than 200 million gallons of oil flowing in the Gulf of Mexico, soiling hundreds of miles of coastline. In this accident, thousands of fishes and animals died due to the oil diffusion. CNT aerogels are considered as an economic and efficient way to clean up oil slicks on sea water. In the article of Zhu^[13], 1 g CNT aerogel can absorb more than 90 g oil in weigh, which was 12 to 13.5 times larger than fiber fabric and woolen (7.5 g and 6.74 g, respectively). What's more, the ultra-flyweight CNT aerogel made by Sun^[14] can absorb 320 g oil per gram. However, both of them have complicated synthesis methods, which needs sol-gel processing and goes through liquid phase. This causes cost raising and hard to enlarge production.

In this paper, we introduced floating catalyst chemical vapor deposition (FCCVD) method^[15] to fabricate CNT aerogel directly, which synthesis aerogel more efficiently at lower cost. We explored its mechanical and oil absorption capacity, and investigated the feasibility of being a kind of oil clean up material.

2 EXPERIMENT METHOD

2.1 Fabrication of FCCVD CNT aerogel

As shown in the fig.1a, tube furnace was used as the reaction zone. Argon was pumped into the quartz tube to evacuate the air. The ethanol with 1% ferrocene and thiophene atomized and injected into quartz tube, after the tube was heated up to 1300°C with the heating rate of 5°C per min. Under the atmosphere of hydrogen and argon, CNTs were produced in the tube and formed self-assembled 3D network floating in the air flow. After a period time, the CNT 3D network stacked at the end of quartz tube and a free-standing monolithic cylindrical CNT aerogel was got at last.

2.2 The measurement of the compressive property

The compressive property was measured by the Instron universal testing machine equipped with a 10N load cell. The test is under the set strain rate of 20mm/min for 10 cycles. Loading and unloading stress-strain curves were simultaneously recorded.

2.3 The pollutant and oil removal test procedure

We used p-xylene to act as the substitutes of oil, and solvent blue 36 acted as indicator. The oil was dropped on the water in a culture dish to simulate the oil leaking on sea. 2 cm*2 cm CNT aerogel was cut and weighed, then put on the oil surface to absorb oil. After 1 min absorbing, the aerogel was weighed to calculate the absorption capacity.

Figure 1: a. the schematic showing the production of the directly FCCVD CNT aerogel; b. the optical graph of the directly FCCVD CNT aerogel; c. and d. SEM images of different magnifications of the directly FCCVD CNT aerogel.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characteristics of the CNT aerogel

This method is easier than traditional sol-gel processing, and it can use micro-molecule hydrocarbon to synthesize CNTs in the gas phase. The CNT aerogel is a stack of random 3D CNT network. Fig.1b shows an optical graph about the monolithic cylindrical CNT aerogel about 53.4 mm in length and 38.8 mm in diameter compared with coin. The aerogel is soft and easy to deform. A strong response can be felt when pressing on the aerogel surface. The SEM image of the CNT aerogel is shown in fig.1c. CNTs are interconnected with each other to form 3D framework with huge number of pores. The sizes of pores are less than micron, which can be used as oil absorbent without any treatment. Another SEM image (fig.1d) with larger magnification shows there is amorphous carbon (AC) at the interconnection points producing “crosslinked” points of CNTs, which can increase the interaction between CNTs and makes stronger mechanical response under external force.

3.2 The compressive property of the CNT aerogel

The result of the compressive property of the CNT aerogel is shown in the fig.2a, the loading and unloading stress curve up to the strain of 80% indicates the structural flexibility and softness of the

aerogel, which shows the aerogel can sustain large deformations without fracture and recover most of the volume back. The curve can go back to the origin above the x axis, which shows the complete recovery without any plastic deformation. The 10 times cyclic compression curve indicates the moderate structure of the CNT aerogel.

The large compressive deformation is contributed to the huge number of pores in the aerogel. When compressive force is applied on the aerogel, the active CNT segments between connection points will bend and align along the perpendicular direction of the applied force, and the pores will be squeezed. The compressive elasticity comes from the AC at the interconnection points. The AC fastens the connection between CNTs, which leads to harder inter-tube slippage and more stable structure.

Figure 2: a. the cyclic compressive curve of the FCCVD CNT aerogel; b. the photograph showing the hydrophobicity of CNT aerogel, in which the contact angle between water droplet and CNT aerogel surface is more than 120° ; c. the CNT aerogel floating on the water surface, due to its ultralight and hydrophobicity; d. the oil absorption test of the CNT aerogel, it can be seen that most p-xylene is absorbed by the CNT aerogel after 1 min; e. the p-xylene is squeezed out from aerogel, and then the aerogel can recover to original shape by adding p-xylene.

3.3 Absorption capacity of the CNT aerogel

The CNT aerogel is a kind of ultralight materials with a density of 12 mg/cm^3 . The contact angle between the CNT aerogel surface and water is more than 120° and water droplet forms a water ball on the surface of the CNT aerogel (fig.2b), which indicates the highly hydrophobicity. The

hydrophobicity and lightweight makes it easily to float on the surface of water (fig.2c). It has a specific surface area of 148 m²/g, indicating high porosity. Thus, we investigated the absorption capacity of CNT aerogel. The experiment is based on the mass and separated into two parts. One is using enough oil to test the limit of absorption capacity, and another is using 1 g oil to test the rate of absorption. Using a 120 mm culture dish as the container, a water layer about 10 mm was placed in the dish, then 1 g p-xylene with solvent blue 36 was dropped on the surface of water. When putting the aerogel on the surface, it was clear that the p-xylene at the contact surface was removed immediately, then the p-xylene around the CNT aerogel was absorbed and further p-xylene obviously float to CNT aerogel due to differential concentration and surface tension. The results show that this CNT aerogel has a wonderful absorption capacity. A CNT aerogel with 0.0216 g can absorb 2.011 g p-xylene, about more than 90 times than its own weight. After 1 min placing, it can be seen that more than 98% p-xylene has been removed from the water surface.

The oil removal from the aerogel is easy and it just needs press the aerogel. With the force applied on the aerogel, most oil will be squeezed out and the CNT aerogel is densified to a thin film. When adding oil on the aerogel, the aerogel can still absorb and recover to the original size. The excellent compressive properties together with wonderful absorption capacity make the CNT aerogel a reusable absorbent of leaking oil film.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The synthesis method of the FCCVD CNT aerogel is more efficient than the traditional processing way, because all the steps are in air phase and continuous. It is easy to expand production by enlarging the equipment. The aerogel shows excellent compressive property, with a compress strain up to 80% without failure. And the high porosity gives the wonderful organic solvent absorption capacity, and the CNT aerogel can absorb 90 times organic solvent than its own weight. Combined compressive property and absorption capacity, the FCCVD CNT aerogel can act as a reusable absorbent of oil film on sea, which can avoid more pollution when the oil spill crisis happens.

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